

INDIRECT TAXES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF ACCOUNTING IN THE TAX SYSTEM

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Annotation. in this scientific article, it is necessary to reform the tax system, to formulate the "digital economy", which is further improving and increasing the efficiency and development of indirect taxes, as well as to accelerate the implementation of universally recognized international norms and standards in the tax sphere into the national tax legislation. To reduce the level of the hidden economy in our country, to conduct business activities, including the creation of competitive conditions equal to the account of regulation and reduction of the burden of indirect taxes, compliance with the requirements of tax legislation is reflected in the reform of procedures on the basis of modern information technology.

Keywords: state budget, indirect taxes, tax system, indirect taxes burden, tax legislation, the mechanism of indirect taxes, tax cuts, curved taxes, straight taxes, tax receipts, Value Added Tax, import, customs duty, excise tax, customs duties

Introduction

Large-scale reforms are being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan through measures aimed at creating favorable conditions for conducting business activities in the tax sphere and improving the investment climate.

It is necessary to reform the tax system, further improve indirect taxation, formulate the "digital economy", which is an increase and development of efficiency, as well as accelerate the implementation of universally recognized international norms and standards in the tax sphere into the national tax legislation.

To reduce the level of the hidden economy in our country, to conduct business activities, including to create competitive conditions equal to the account of regulation and reduction of indirect tax burden, to reform procedures for compliance with the requirements of tax legislation on the basis of modern information technologies and simplify its procedure.

The president of the Republic of Uzbekistan's address to the 24th Yanvar Oliy Majlis in 2020 and the strategy of action on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "year of development of Science,

Education and digital economy "were determined to ensure the implementation of the tasks defined in the state program on

In the appeal of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis in 2020 24 January, it was noted that in accordance with the new tax code, which was recently adopted, many innovations will be introduced into practice from this year:

"According to the recently adopted new tax code, many innovations are being introduced into practice from this year. In particular, the types of taxes were reduced from 13 to 9 units. In order to allow the payment of taxes to be made on time or in-place, the enacted tax regulations were introduced.

The norms of the tax code should be meticulously mastered by every tax officer, entrepreneur and taxpayer, for which it is necessary to train them on a regular basis"[1].

It was also noted that in the appeal of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis of December 29, 2020, practical assistance was provided to state-owned enterprises and more than 500 thousand business entities and nearly 8 million citizens on tax benefits and financial support for a total of 66 trillion soums:

"In order to mitigate and eliminate the consequences of the pandemic, measures were taken by the state for a total of 82 trillion soums. In particular, the anti-Crisis Fund was established and more than 16 trillion soums were allocated from the budget for the activities related to the fight against the coronavirus and the support of the population and enterprises. In addition, state-owned enterprises and more than 500 thousand business entities and nearly 8 million citizens were provided with practical assistance in terms of tax benefits, loan terms and financial support for a total of 66 trillion soums" [2].

At present, all necessary conditions are created for the functioning of leading spheres and sectors of the country's economy in harmony with the Times. The wide opening of the road to small business and private entrepreneurship, consistent implementation of the tax system using advanced information and communication technologies constitute a solid foundation of our fruitful achievements. As a result of the extensive reforms carried out in the tax sphere, the economy of our country develops with stable standards and creates a basis for further improvement of the business environment.

Depending on the economic essence, taxes are divided into crooked and straight taxes or direct and indirect taxes. The legal payers of indirect taxes are the senders who download the product (work, service). But those who really pay the weight of the tax to the budget are consumers of goods (work, service), that is, indirect taxes all fall

directly on consumers. These taxes are put in addition on the cost of the goods (work, service).

On the positive side of indirect taxes, they limit the withdrawal of working capital from the Republic, contribute to the prosperity of the country, as well as slightly curb the level of inflation (the mass of excess money in circulation), which limits the withdrawal of working capital from the country. A reasonable increase in the rate of indirect taxes does not directly affect the financial end of the activities of enterprises, that is, it does not reduce investment activity.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Professor Q.A. According to yahyoev, "depending on the economic essence, taxes are divided into crooked and correct taxes, or directly and indirectly. The right taxes are paid directly by the taxpayer himself, that is, both the taxpayer and the real payer of the tax will be one person. ladi. To ' the situation of increasing the tax burden on others will not be here. These taxes are paid from all income and include all property taxes.

Crooked taxpayers of taxes are the senders (service providers) who download the product (work, service). But even from the weight of the tax to the budget payers are consumers of goods (work, service), that is, real taxpayers are hiding here." - described as. [3].

Professor A.V. Vahobov, A. Jo 'raevs indirectly dwell on taxes," the legal payers of curved taxes are the senders who download the product (work, service). But those who really pay the weight of the tax to the budget are those who consume the goods (work, service), that is, all of the crooked taxes directly fall under the responsibility of consumers. These taxes are put in addition on the value of the goods (work, service)", he added. [4]

M.M. Shadurskaya, E.A. Blueberries, T.V. Bakunovas touched upon indirect taxes and described it as " indirect taxes are a tax in the form of an additional price imposed on goods and services." [5]

Research methodology

In this article, scientific works of scientists of foreign and National Economists devoted to the types of indirect taxes, the role of indirect taxes in the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the peculiarities of indirect taxes are studied. In the analysis of the data of the state tax administration of the Republic of Uzbekistan statistical methods of grouping, comparative analysis, selection were used. Comparative analysis of literature, logical and structural analysis, grouping and comparative comparison, economic-statistical analysis and comparative analysis, sampling observation methods were used as research methodology.

Analysis and results

By 2021, the state accounted for 35.8% of the direct revenue budget, and bilvosit soliklarning-34.2% in relation to the roof. Income in the annual composition of the tour according to the dynamics of the 1st chart of the crossatilgan.

1-diagram. The share of the state budget in total revenues (%)

The composition of the state budget revenues was influenced by the change in tax policy measures of the last three years, the abolition of previously issued tax incentives, the establishment of a tax base on the account of reforms carried out in the economic sectors, as well as the prices of raw materials and Commodity Futures.

The change in the composition of tax revenues is also associated with an increase in the number of taxpayers for certain types of taxes.

Revenues from indirect taxes in 2021 year amounted to 9,9 trillion in comparison with last year. SA ' increased by 21,2%, 56,3 trillion. made up the sum.

Receipts for Value Added Tax, which will be administrated by the tax and customs authorities in 2021 year, are 52,8 trillion TL. sum (without taking into account the amount of compensation) or 2020 trillion, compared with 12,6 years. increased soy.(2-diagram)

2-diagram. Information on Value Added Tax receipts and reimbursement

Bunda 2020 Value – Added Tax levied by customs authorities in comparison with the year increased by 38,2%, the tax authorities levied-by 24,8%. The growth of revenues is provided for the account of the establishment of the tax base (tax reform and abolition of tax benefits), economic growth (including mitigation of quarantine restrictions in 2020), as well as measures to improve tax and Customs Administration.

In addition to ensuring that the value added tax is fully borne in the budget, the procedure for tax substitution is being improved, which occurs as a result of an increase in the amount of Value Added Tax that is taken into account from the amount of the calculated tax.

Until July 1, 2020, only the role of Value Added Tax on export companies was covered. Starting from July 1, 2020, a system has been introduced that allows all companies to compensate for Value Added Tax and set deadlines.

Also in 2020 year to taxpayers 9,0 trillion. if the sum is returned, the amount of compensation in 2021 is 14,4 trillion. amount (27,3% of the funds received).14.4 trillion. when calculating the amount of compensation in the amount of sum, the proceeds from Value Added Tax in 2021 year amounted to 38,4 trillion TL in the report. the sum was reflected in the amount (reduced to the amount of compensation of receipts).

The measures taken to create a competitive environment equal to the account of the abolition of tax and Customs privileges, as well as to improve the administration of the collection of Value Added Tax, have made it possible to

increase the efficiency of Value Added Tax. International financial institutions use the effective ad valorem coefficient of Value Added Tax when analyzing income from Value Added Tax. This is explained by the fact that different countries apply different tax rates and tax substitution procedures. This is explained by the fact that the average figure for the IHTT countries is around 60%, which is due to the presence of non-taxable turnover and reduced rates of value added.

The efficiency of Value Added Tax (on aggregation) increased from 44,5% in 2020 year to 48% in 2021 year. (VAT collection efficiency = income from VAT in interest from VAT / VAT rate).

In 2021, the excise tax revenues in 2020 year amounted to 1,4 trillion TL. increased so and 13,1 trillion. made up the sum. The increase in revenues was provided mainly on account of the indexation of tax rates to an average of 2021% in February and October 15 years.

In this case, the excise tax receipts on alcohol products remained at the level of 2020 year, despite the fact that the rates were indexed. Reduction of the excise tax on imports from August 1, 2020-for vehicles and from January 1, 2021 – 73 commodity positions (food, electric appliances, etc.) related to cancellation. For these reasons, the volume of imports of excise duty-free products amounted to 978,6 million US dollars. Us \$ 557.6 million. Reduced to US dollars.

At the same time, the abolition of excise taxes on goods of a separate type allowed to legalize their official imports. Bunda, for example, in 2021 year sausage products grew by almost 4 times compared to import 2020 year.

In 2021, customs duty receipts 4,8 trillion. sum or 2020 trillion compared with 1,2 years. increased soy. Despite the fact that the customs duty revenue has increased by an absolute amount, its share in the total revenues of the state budget is maintained within 2-3%.

At the same time, the period of application of the zero rate of customs duty on importation into the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 20 types of tavar was extended until December 31, 2021. List of them "coronavirus pandemic" of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 3, 2020

PF-5978"on additional measures to support the population, economic sectors and business entities in the period" is presented in the decree. In 2021, the amount of benefits amounted to 480.0 billion. made up the sum.

It should be noted that the share of imports subject to customs duties in the total volume of imports in 2021 year amounted to 68.9%.[6]

Conclusion.

As already mentioned above, direct and indirect taxes are interrelated with each other, forming a single tax system. The role of indirect taxes in European countries is higher than in the US, Japan, Canada and Australia. In World tax practice, it is possible to estimate the level of development of the economy of this or that country, depending on the ratio of direct and indirect taxes in the structure of the state budget revenues. In European countries, the incidence of indirect taxes in the volume of total tax revenues is higher than 45 percent, in some countries it is 55 percent. The group of countries with this figure above 50 percent includes Mexico, Turkey and Korea. In the USA, Japan, Canada and Austria, this figure is 15-20 per cent.

In increasing the importance of indirect taxes in the tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following measures should be taken:

-As the most priority task within the framework of improving the tax policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, consistent reduction of the burden of indirect taxes, simplification of the taxation system and improvement of tax administration are the most important conditions for the rapid development of the economy and improvement of the country's investment attractiveness.

-Changes and additions to the tax legislation on indirect taxes are one of the main factors in improving the living standards of the population of Uzbekistan and increasing gross income.

-Businesses should also not be excluded from the account even if the impact on the cost of the product by increasing their Real income through systematic facilitation of the burden of indirect taxes is low. As a result of this, it is proposed to consistently study the range of products produced (services rendered) and to further expand the scope of benefits provided for by taxation.

-Activity of economic entities and citizens is required in the implementation of the tax policy on improving indirect taxation.

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